

www.bjisrd.com

Methodology for Forming the Creative Ability of Future Primary Teachers

M. Toshtemirova,

Andijan State University, basic doctoral student

Abstract: *this article describes the methods of forming the creativity of future primary school teachers.*

Key words: *education, training, knowledge, thinking, creativity, creativity, competence, technology, imagination, ability, abstract idea.*

Introduction. Using students' creativity in education greatly helps them to assimilate knowledge and develop creative imagination. Teaching creativity is not only possible, but also necessary. R. Stenberg developed a theory of creativity based on six specific, interconnected sources of development of creative activity:

1. Abilities: synthetic (the ability to see problems in a new world and to think outside the box); analytical (the ability to analyze and evaluate ideas); practical-contextual (the ability to find ways to apply abstract ideas in practice).
2. Knowledge. According to R. Stenberg, there is a U-shaped relationship between knowledge and creativity. He emphasizes that knowledge can limit the coherence of thinking. He tried to draw this conclusion on the example of scientists, that is, those who, without having sufficient knowledge, make a significant contribution to science in the early years of their career. The scientist's conclusions can also be confirmed by A. Einstein's statement that "Imagination is more important than knowledge."
3. Thinking. R. Stenberg, through the analysis of thinking methods, comes to the conclusion that a method inherent in the laws of nature is important for creativity: "personal laws of the movement of thoughts are created."
4. Personal qualities. Almost all scientists have emphasized the importance of personal qualities for the creative process. Personal qualities inherent in the creative process include: overcoming various frustrations, readiness for intellectual risk, patience with uncertainty, and self-confidence.

5. Motivation. Empirical observations confirm that people can create truly creative work in an area they do not like. Because they are so absorbed in what they do not like, they do not even think about the reward.
6. Environment. Of course, without a favorable environment, creativity will not be a bright manifestation. Because the components of creativity need compensation. If the motivation for the creative process is not good, the environment can compensate for it[59].

Research methodology. Also, according to foreign scholars, the “12 strategies of creativity” also play an important role in primary education:

1. To set an example for imitation (if one wants to learn creativity, one must seek its source within oneself).
2. To support and encourage doubts that arise from the point of view of attitude towards generally accepted rules (to teach everyone to recognize things and situations that are worth doubting).
3. The right to make mistakes (fear of making mistakes leads to unpreparedness for accidents, inability to think independently).
4. Encourage intellectual risk (creative individuals should be able to take risks, because they go down a path that others have not taken).
5. Organize the learning process in ways that allow students to demonstrate their creative potential. When presenting learning tasks, it is effective to rely on phrases such as "imagine...", "what would you suggest...", "describe...", "state your guess."
6. Encourage the skill of searching, formulating, and redefining the problem (the skill of making choices is a necessary skill).
7. Encourage and reward creative ideas and the results of creative activity (students feel a special need for their teachers to appreciate the results of their creative activity at all times).
8. Make time for creative thinking (creativity is a process that requires time and time for thinking).
9. Encourage curiosity and curiosity about ambiguity (ideas that emerge as a result of “not stopping” in times of time pressure and uncertainty are temporary and undesirable).
10. Prepare for various disappointments that may come your way (creativity is not only creative thinking, but also not holding back).
11. Encourage the desire to continue (instill in students the idea that "creativity has no boundaries").
12. Seek and find the connection between the creative person and the environment (students should be prepared to either seek and find or create such conditions for their creative talent to find encouragement).

Discussion. Based on the above ideas, R. Stenberg, along with the ideas of other authors, can rightly be considered the father of the psychology of creativity. He proposed analytical, synthetic and practical abilities, which include divergence in his theory of investment, problems with the new world, seeing aspects that others do not pay attention to, and creating a whole from isolated situations, play an important role in synthetic abilities.

In the works of A. Maslow and K. Rogers, the following criteria related to the manifestation of creativity were identified: feeling the problem; ability to generalize, perceive similarities and understand differences; divergent thinking, high speed of thinking.

American researchers (J. Guilford) have developed a system of tests to identify and develop a person's creative abilities in order to distinguish children with high creativity and high intelligence. Children with high intelligence, on the other hand, are able to achieve standard achievements, match the standards set by adults and teachers, while children with high creativity approach success in a different way from the generally accepted ones. Such children are usually "on fire", distinguished by their rebelliousness. The study found that teachers prefer to teach children with high general intelligence and low levels of creativity. Students with creative abilities tend to have a high level of imagination and a sense of humor. Teachers do not always have a positive attitude towards such students. For our research, the term "divergent thinking", introduced into science by J. Guilford, is of particular importance. He identified such parameters of divergent thinking as speed, originality, coherence and clarity of thinking, as well as imagination.

E. Torrance created a test of inventiveness and "Creative Abilities in Situations and Actions" to measure children's creativity. They are scientifically called the "Torrance Tests" and are intended for use with children ages 5 and up.

The monograph entitled "Gifted Children" highlights the following aspects of creativity: 1) enthusiasm, curiosity, and immersion in work; 2) demonstrating a high level of mental strength; 3) independence; 4) inventiveness in using games, materials, and ideas; 5) expressing a variety of thoughts about a specific situation; 6) the ability to approach the problem in different ways, to use available opportunities (adaptability); 7) the ability to search for and find original ideas.

Also, when assessing the formation of creativity, one can rely on the model of B. Lucas. It separately identifies some components of creativity.

1. Curiosity (strong desire to complete the task): Interest in the world around (task description) and the desire to learn more about the world (various aspects of the task; telling fantasies);

Conclusion. Independently search for an answer to one's own question. Actively search for new information from various sources.

B. Lucas's model for assessing the formation of creativity

1. Development of ideas.

Two aspects are distinguished in this:

originality of the proposed ideas;

flexibility and mobility, the ability to develop ideas of different types.

3. Development of proposed ideas.

evaluation of proposed ideas from different perspectives, studying their strengths and weaknesses in order to improve or reject them;

the ability to quickly adapt one's activities to the circumstances as new information about the research object appears.

References:

1. Downing James P., Creative Teaching: Ideas to Boost Student Interest, Englewood, Colo.: Teacher Ideas Press, 1997. – 225 p.
2. Зиновкина М.М. Многоуровневое непрерывное креативное образование в школе // Концепт. – 2012. – № 9 (сентябрь). – ART 12116. – 1,0 п. л.

3. Зиновкина М.М. Многоуровневое непрерывное креативное образование: Сб. науч.тр. МГИУ. – М.: МГИУ, 2002. – 310 с.
4. Зиновкина М.М. НФТМ-ТРИЗ: креативное образование XXI века. Теория и практика. Монография. – М.: МГИУ, 2008. – 306 с.